

THE PARTICIPATION OF BUKHARIAN JEWS IN THE ECONOMIC LIFE OF THE ZARAFSHAN OASIS DURING THE INDEPENDENCE PERIOD

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the participation of Bukharan Jews in the economic life of the Zarafshan Valley during Uzbekistan's independence period (1991–2020). It highlights their involvement in trade, handicrafts, and small entrepreneurship, as well as the impact of migration on the regional economy.*

Keywords: *Bukharan Jews, Zarafshan Valley, independence period, trade, entrepreneurship, migration.*

Annotasiya. *Ushbu maqolada mustaqillik davrida (1991–2020-yillar) Buxoro yahudiylarining Zarafshon vohasi iqtisodiy hayotidagi ishtiroki tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqotda ularning savdo-sotiq, hunarmandchilik va kichik tadbirkorlik sohalaridagi faoliyati hamda migratsiya jarayonlarining mintaqa iqtisodiyotiga ta'siri yoritilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Buxoro yahudiylari, Zarafshon vohasi, mustaqillik davri, savdo-sotiq, hunarmandchilik, tadbirkorlik, migratsiya.*

Аннотация. *В статье рассматривается участие бухарских евреев в экономической жизни Зарафшанской долины в период независимости Узбекистана (1991–2020 гг.). Проанализирована их деятельность в сфере торговли, ремесел и малого предпринимательства, а также влияние миграционных процессов на экономику региона.*

Ключевые слова: *бухарские евреи, Зарафшанская долина, период независимости, торговля, предпринимательство, миграция.*

Introduction. Following Uzbekistan's attainment of independence, political and economic reforms were implemented in the country, initiating the transition to a market economy. This process brought about significant changes in the economic life of the Zarafshan Oasis as well. Alongside various nationalities and ethnic groups, Bukharian Jews actively participated in these processes, conducting their activities primarily in the fields of commerce, craftsmanship, services, and small business.

During the initial years of independence, Bukharian Jews adapted to market relations by relying on their historically formed commercial experience and professional skills. In the cities of Samarkand and Bukhara, their activities in retail trade, jewelry-making, tailoring, and the service sector had a positive impact on the development of the local market infrastructure.

Discussion and Results. Beginning in the 1990s, emigration processes abroad intensified among Bukharian Jews. Although this situation led to a quantitative decline in their population within the region, the remaining Jewish population continued their economic activities. In some instances, it was observed that investments flowed into the local economy through the financial and commercial networks of the diaspora residing abroad.

In this process, the connections established with foreign Jewish organizations and diasporas assumed particular importance. Specifically, financial and organizational assistance was provided by Jewish communities in Israel, the USA, and European countries. During holidays

(such as Pesach, the primary Jewish festival) and several exhibitions organized by the Jewish Cultural Center (known as "Shalom" since 2001), material aid was provided by the "Sokhnut" charitable organization in Tashkent and the "Vyshikyntam" society in Zurich, Switzerland. This situation demonstrates that during the early years of independence, external resources entered the Zarafshan Oasis through international non-governmental and religious organizations.

Furthermore, visits to Bukhara by representatives of the State of Israel and US officials carried significant weight, not only diplomatically but also socio-economically. Specifically, a 1991 ceremony organized by the Jewish National-Cultural Center to mark the 13th birthday (Bar Mitzvah) of 32 adolescents was attended by Chief Rabbi of Jerusalem David Nisanov and Israeli religious community figures Avraham Bagiev and Binyamin Gulkarov. Following this, Israeli Ambassador Aryeh Levin visited Bukhara on February 18–20, 1992. On November 12, 1997, US President Bill Clinton and First Lady Hillary Rodham Clinton visited our country, touring the historic cities of Samarkand and Bukhara, where they visited the Bukharian Jewish Synagogue and met with ordinary citizens. Additionally, US Secretary of State Madeleine Albright paid an official visit to Uzbekistan on April 16–19, 2000.

Through these visits, officials familiarized themselves with the living conditions, religious freedom, and cultural environment of Bukharian Jews, highly evaluating the policies implemented to ensure interethnic harmony in the region. Consequently, although the Bukharian Jewish population decreased quantitatively during the independence period, it is evident that they maintained a certain level of activity in the economic and social life of the Zarafshan Oasis through institutional and international connections.

Conclusion. In conclusion, the economic participation of the Jewish community during the independence period was manifested primarily in three directions:

First, through charitable and philanthropic activities. For instance, the financial assistance provided by the "JDC" (Joint) society of New York to students and low-income families contributed to the socio-economic stability of the Zarafshan Oasis.

Second, through the mobilization of economic resources via international connections. The visits of the Israeli Ambassador and other foreign guests facilitated the integration of the local Jewish community into international economic and cultural networks.

Third, through active participation in the local economic environment. The historical activity of the Jewish population in the spheres of commerce, craftsmanship, and the service sector was sustained during the years of independence, successfully adapting to the market economy.

Despite the quantitative decline of the Bukharian Jewish population during the independence period, they participated both directly and indirectly in the economic life of the Zarafshan Oasis. Through international financial support, charity, commerce, and service industries, they contributed significantly to the socio-economic development of the region.

References

1. State Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Statistics. Population censuses and demographic indicators.
2. Saidov A., Qodirov S. *Mustaqillik yillarida O'zbekistonda etnik jarayonlar* [Ethnic processes in Uzbekistan during the years of independence]. Tashkent. 2010.

3. Jewish Virtual Library. Bukharan Jews after 1991. <https://www.jewishvirtuallibrary.org>
4. Xolmatov A. Zarafshon vohasida bozor iqtisodiyotining shakllanishi [Formation of the market economy in the Zarafshan Oasis]. Samarkand. 2014.
5. Юхан Бен Ямин. “День после Ханука, Рамадана и Крисмаса.” [The day after Hanukkah, Ramadan, and Christmas]. 2001. Bjew.com. <http://www.bukharianjews.com>.
6. Mavlon Shukurzoda. AQSh–O‘zbekiston hamkorligi fakt va raqamlarda [US–Uzbekistan cooperation in facts and figures]. Tashkent: "Niso Poligraf". 2016.
7. Bazarova M., Abdulloeva G., Kuziev N. Buxoro viloyatida faoliyat olib borayotgan milliy madaniy markazlar [National cultural centers operating in the Bukhara region]. Umrboqiy Meros Publishing House.
8. Internet resources.